
Twitter Profile Information based on Feature Levels for the Identification of Individuals

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Abstract:

The objective of a biometric method is to make a human-like decision about identifying an individual based on physiological or potentially social characteristics. Due to the low quality of the data, biometric-based recognition schemes can be exceptionally confounded. In order for a computerized biometric framework to make decisions consistently and dynamically, Social Behavioral (SB) prompts are essential. A system that identifies an individual person on the social network (SN) is proposed in order to improve the efficiency of the traditional biometric frameworks. The social-behavioural cues of individual people were extracted from an online tweeter network. A study shows that social biometric features are more effective than biometric features based on rank. A person's score is determined by the Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PMCC) based on the SB attributes. Furthermore, the correlation coefficient is used to calculate four different SBB features. The impact of absolute scores with their SBB model is tested directly from the OSN datasets for various kinds of subjects. Through the use of specific datasets and by comparing registered features with different types of test features, the cross-validation functionality of the system is demonstrated. The proposed system performs better than the conventional biometric framework for identifying individuals. The experimental results using SB fusion techniques demonstrated a recognition rate of 95% and were faster than most other biometric systems. Based on the SB information available on the network, the feature-based fusion technique is the best compromise, and it is commonly applied in multimodal biometric frameworks to improve precision.

Keywords: Biometric Recognition, Fusion, OSN, Person Authentication, SBB, SB Features, Twitter.

I. INTRODUCTION

The trend of communicating via online social networking platforms has become more progressive in recent years [1]. An advantage of the human brain over computer systems is its capacity to conduct a great deal of parallel processing with the equal preparation of assistant data,

such as viewable prompts, intellectual and social conversations, context-oriented information, spatial and temporal information. Social Behavioral Biometrics (SBB) cues from social media play an important role in-person authentication. The study explores the user's cognitive behavior on Online Social Networking (OSN) [2]. In most cases, it is used nowadays to prevent fraud because each individual interacts with a digital device uniquely, and his/her behavior can be discerned from an imposter's. The system uses a fusion of rank weighting and score weighting to identify individuals using 241 Twitter datasets [3]. Experimental results show that the users' profiles have the most notable effect over other social biometric traits. After cross-approval, the system achieved around 99.45% accuracy by using genetic algorithms based on score level combinations. A work not included in the profile may explore each other's characteristics over time in order to improve the performance. The OSN profile information, such as re-tweets, replies, link contributions, and the current trends, is considered with a customary face and ear biometric system [4]. In contrast to customary biometric frameworks, the test results on person's identification are significantly higher. To further improve online social behavior, a comprehensive analysis is needed. Authors investigated the feasibility of identifying people using social network activities such as behavioural biometrics [5]. Researchers are analyzing several idiosyncratic features extracted from social media sites as novel biometric social behavior biomarkers. The concept to a variety of online social environments and develop new communication-based features is necessary for research. An SBB analysis includes networks including Uniform Resource Locator (URL), re-tweet, temporal, reply, and hash tag networks collected from nearly 241 tweets for person recognition [6]. The data will also be validated as a tool for behavior recognition, which will further strengthen the presented findings. Individual biometrics (face, ear or signature) are classified using matching score methodology at the first level [7]. To reduce error rates, social network (SN) analysis is used to reinforce the confidence level of the classifier. To arrive at a final decision, the results of individual biometric classifications are fused together in the second level. The SN should be improved by studying different approaches to centrality analysis. Besides confidence-based SN classifiers, other types of biometric fusions should also be considered. Authors propose an intelligent add-on for smart devices to enable continuous verification of users [8]. A number of mobile apps with social networking capabilities were analyzed for usage statistics and data from built-in sensors. Machine learning techniques are used to analyze the collected feature set. By aggregating behavior patterns from five social media apps, the system can verify genuine users with up to 97% success rate. Further system needs more significant feature of social networking information to improve accuracy of the system. Aspect-based feature extraction is used to extract specific sentiments on Twitter data with various aspects of services, which is then used as an input to Bi-directional Gated Recurrent Unit (BGRU) for classification [9]. By incorporating self-attention layers into BGRU, the learning rate is further enhanced. In order to evaluate the efficiencies of the method are evaluated through experiments based on the accuracy, precision, recall, and f-scores of real-time collected tweets. Comparing the developed method to traditional approaches: Long-short term memory (LSTM) and standard GRU, the developed approach achieved 80.4% accuracy,

81% precision, 80% recall, and f-score for 1000 dataset lengths. A better performance could be achieved by analyzing Twitter data further. On the other hand, an extractor system is proposed that shows trending hashtags and active users as bars in a graph [10]. Tweets from the current location are displayed on a map in the Tweet analyzer. Many real-world applications can be leveraged with it, such as business intelligence, job search, or news updates. This tool would perform better if it had unlimited storage space in the cloud. For faster processing, scalability, and resilience, distributed processing can also be applied to Identify users within a single account using social media data and community detection algorithms [11]. An algorithm utilizes the program-based network diagrams to identify communities through micro blog user information retrieved from electronic program guides. The proposed method shows greater efficiency in recommendation. Using supervised based learning methods for feature extraction and prediction, the author investigates the patterns spreading about rumors on Twitter propagation by analyzing user interactions in social media and the underlying messages [12]. To improve the performance of the system, more Twitter analysis is required. Authenticates genuine accounts versus fake accounts using the writing style on SN [13]. A supervised machine learning algorithm is trained to build the knowledge base. It consists of extracting the relevant features and then comparing them to all the features in the knowledge base to determine the similarity. The most similar vector is identified as the verified account but for larger number of accounts and evaluates its effectiveness and robustness needs to be more relevant features. Using messages from Twitter of 140 characters as the maximum length data source, this study examines how to identify authors in short texts far below this threshold [14]. Even for small dataset sizes of 60 training instances per author, we achieve classification accuracy close to that of longer texts. A minimum threshold for author identification does not hold true for style marker feature sets. Writing profiles of users on OSN will provide its significance, if such kinds of profiles add to SBB [15] [16]. There are unique features of the SBB that are drawn from the social behavior information of Twitter. Individuals can recognize a proof framework based on user profiles, re-tweets, replies, web links, and current trends in the OSN profiles. Researchers can identify participants' records based on their activities, particularly on social media, because these activities may reveal their identity and membership in research programs [17]. The use of social media has granted scientists unprecedented data to study human behavior associated with medical conditions and treatments on a variety of levels, ranging from cohort-level discussions to analyses of sentiment at the population level [18]. The effect of social media on participant maintenance, discusses several key considerations related to the inclusion of social media in longitudinal research, and discusses factors that influence engagement in research-related social media [19].

Social media are a key component, which offers researchers the opportunity to examine practitioners and their practices in deeper and more in-depth ways [20]. By applying distraction-conflict theory to the literature on social media, technostress, and addiction, one can theorize that social media in the workplace can induce technostress, and subsequently, Internet addiction [21]. By investigating the factors that encourage a social media follower or fan to turn into an actual purchaser, researchers can unfold the role of social media in Indonesia for business activities [22].

Various social media platforms provide a wide spectrum of interactive options for interacting with consumers and taking them through the various decisions of each step of the marketing funnel with their whole network of connections [23]. Its low cost, ease of access, and fast dissemination make social media an appealing media outlet for news consumption [24]. Detecting fake news is an essential task that ensures users receive genuine information and maintains trust in the news ecosystem. To determine the ratio of tweets and Facebook posts with information about social impact in relation to all social media data pertaining to a particular research work, the social impact coverage ratio is defined [25].

Designing an efficient and privacy-preserving SB-based biometric authentication system is proposed in order to improve security. This paper explores how the presence of SBB traits affects a person's identification. Also, it intends to utilize writing profiles and the conversion of textual content into meaningful vectors [26] in order to calculate individual PMCC scores, as well as calculating SBB attributes from PMCC's: a) An innovative SBB attribute is suggested from the tweets of the users, which are collected on OSN, and their responses over time is based on their involvement in social networks. b) System attributes can enhance the performance of the SB profile and enable implementation of the SBB during the evaluation process and calculate the absolute scores using PMCC and then calculate four different SBB features based on the correlation coefficient. c) The impact of absolute scores with their SBB model is tested directly from the OSN datasets for different kinds of subjects. d) The cross-validation of the system is demonstrated by using specific datasets and comparing the registered parameters with different kinds of test parameters that are not part of the registered process.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

OSN users exchange social information in different ways, it is quite likely that Twitter is the most well-known online platform in spite of the fact that it is used by and a large number of people worldwide. Twitter has approximately millions of dynamic users worldwide. The information contained in tweets are overburdened with personal information and social relationships. A tweet kind of data is used in the proposed system: 1) The textual information from tweets is extracted, such as hash tags and web links, and the interactions on the social network reveal the users' involvement, such as re-tweets and replies.

2) These data are compiled to create the SBB profiles for authentication. 3) As an example, a reply from a specific user is continuously created, which is associated with the corresponding user nodes, and users share their current trend topic which can be displayed as a hash-tag on SN.

A new technique, SB approach, has been introduced for authentication of people in biometric systems based on their blogging profiles on social networks like Twitter. The four SB attributes are integrated into the proposed system based on their shared SB cues such as hash-tag networks, shared URL-links, re-tweet networks, and reply networks. In order to create a SBB profile for person authentication, a new kind of fusion algorithm is implemented to combine SB attributes. Figure.1 shows the proposed system, where the individual person's four SB attributes, such as

hash-tags, URLs-links, re-tweets and replies, are taken from Twitter.

Calculate the absolute scores using PMCC, and then compute four different SBB features based on the correlation coefficient. Fusion uses these features as SBB traits for person authentication. In this study, four different feature combinations are analyzed to match the test SBB profiles with the registered features. In the SBB system, only the appropriate features were investigated. Twitter users are able to build their writing profile by accumulating the new collection of tweets; this profile manages the tweets that have high significance for the specific user. Writing statements vary from person to person with some degree of variation on OSN. During this work, the first tasks are to prepare the required data for processing and analysis. Using the Tweeter data mining strategy, the system pre-processes the unsophisticated data by arranging it into a systematic format in order to change it into valuable information. While writing tweets on social media networks, users commonly use unsophisticated information like punctuation marks and putting extra characters, yet these extra characters do not aid feature extraction. As part of the pre-processing stage, all unnecessary characters and marks are removed from the Twitter data, as well as repeatedly occurring tweets.

SBB PROFILE CREATION

Each Twitter dataset is split into a matrix of the separate vocabulary of hash-tags, re-tweets, replies, and URL-links. Figure.2 shows the samples of tweeter data that include replies, hash-tags, URLs, and re-tweets. In the data text classification [32] based on the requirement playing an important role in splitting the text matrix. This paper collects and counts the total number of URL-links and hash tags that appear on Twitter on a monthly basis.

Also count the total re-tweets, replies at each node separately. Using data mined from Twitter, SBB profiles are built using the interactions between users in social media. Several different kinds of interactive data are analyzed: 1) URLs shared among participants, 2) re-tweets, 3) hashtags, and 4) replies. In an analysis of tweets, it was shown that the tendencies of the users were influenced by a small group of friends on their friend list called nodes. Using the different nodes, i.e., reply and re-tweet networks, this work created friend list interaction graphs.

In Figure.3, the number of interactions between the user and the nodes from N1 to Nn is shown as a weight in the reply and re-tweet network. The nodes are only considered if the weight is greater than five. The system considered only those interactive nodes with whom the user had a regular connection and with whom he/she interacted frequently, which were integrated into the system rather than include the total number of followers, i.e., friends' profiles.

SCORE MODEL

Using six-month tweeter data from M1-M6 for an individual with different attributes is used to create the score model as illustrated in table1 and each number represents a weight for the individual person. Using the PMCC [27], the sore of an individual is determined. Two arrangements of information are compared using linear correlation [28], this is the covariance [29]

[30] of the two dynamic factors divided by their standard deviations; accordingly, these are the basic estimations of the covariance of the two SB attributes.

Fig1: Proposed System Illustration

Likewise, covariance itself is limited to reflecting only the direct relationship between factors, and ignores a variety of different types of relationship. Absolute PMCC values fall into a range of 0 to 1. The coefficient generally symbolized by $R_{S_1S_2}$ and mentioned as a sample correlation coefficient between S_1 and S_2 .

USER 1 :

USER 2 :

Fig 2: Example of sample tweets in the dataset contain replies, hash-tags, URLs, and re-tweets.

Fig 3: Reply and re-tweet networks interaction graph

$$R_{S_1 S_2} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_{1i} - \bar{S}_1)(S_{2i} - \bar{S}_2)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_{1i} - \bar{S}_1)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_{2i} - \bar{S}_2)^2}} \quad (1)$$

Table 1. Total sample session a person

Session	Re-tweets (S ₁)	Replies (S ₂)	URLs (S ₃)	Hash-Tags (S ₄)
M1	34	12	35	23
M2	23	30	32	32
M3	36	23	18	15
M4	25	30	28	19
M5	32	31	29	30
M6	34	28	19	30

Obtain an equation for $R_{S_1 S_2}$ by means of estimation of the co-variances and variances based on a sample and is described in Eq. (1), whereas n is the size of the samples, S_{1i}, S_{2i} are the individual sample points indexed with i and $\bar{S}_1 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n S_{1i}$ is the sample mean; and homogenously for $\bar{S}_2$.

Rearranging the Eq. 1 is:

$$R_{S_1 S_2} = \frac{n \sum S_{1i} S_{2i} - \sum S_{1i} \sum S_{2i}}{\sqrt{n \sum S_{1i}^2 - (\sum S_{1i})^2} \sqrt{n \sum S_{2i}^2 - (\sum S_{2i})^2}} \quad (2)$$

The Eq. 2 put forwards a suitable single-pass algorithm for computing sample correlations and once again rearranging the Eq. 2 and then expressed as in Eq. 3 is:

$$R_{S_1 S_2} = \frac{\sum S_{1i} - S_{2i} - n\bar{S}_1\bar{S}_2}{\sqrt{(\sum S_{1i}^2 - n\bar{S}_1^2)} \sqrt{(\sum S_{2i}^2 - n\bar{S}_2^2)}} \quad (3)$$

It provides a consequent expression based on the products of the standard scores as described in Eq.4:

$$R_{S_1 S_2} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{S_{1i} - \bar{S}_1}{K_{S_1}} \right) \left(\frac{S_{2i} - \bar{S}_2}{K_{S_2}} \right) \quad (4)$$

whereas $\left(\frac{S_{1i} - \bar{S}_1}{K_{S_1}} \right)$ is the standard score and homogeneously standard score for S_2 . Alternatively, Eq. 4 can be written it as in Eq. 5:

$$R_{S_1 S_2} = \frac{\sum S_{1i} S_{2i} - n \bar{S}_1 \bar{S}_2}{(n-1) K_{S_1} K_{S_2}} \quad (5)$$

Where $K_{S_1} K_{S_2}$ are described as:

$K_{S_1} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (S_{1i} - \bar{S}_1)^2}$ is the sample standard deviation; and homogeneously for K_{S_2} . As a result of taking the SBB attributes from table 1, the sample PMCC's shown in table 2 are calculated.

and frequently referred to as sample correlation coefficient, PMCC is a metric that depends on the number of samples. These PMCCs are calculated by substituting the sample covariance's and variances into the above equations. An SBB attribute's correlation coefficient is measured to determine how strongly it correlates with another attribute. Relationships are stronger when the number is higher. In the table 2, there is more strong relationship between the re-tweets (S1) and replies (S2).

Table 2. Sample of PMCC 's of a person for six-month Session

PMCC	Absolute Scores
R_{S1-S2}	0.5322
R_{S1-S3}	0.4824
R_{S1-S4}	0.3038
R_{S2-S3}	0.2675
R_{S2-S4}	0.3840
R_{S3-S4}	0.3092

FEATURES EXTRACTION AND SBB PROFILE

This work uses the SBB attributes to identify and classify people, which are derived from PMCC's values of each individual for the six-month session, and then the F_1 , F_2 , F_3 , and F_4 features are calculated using Eq. 6-9. The individual person's SBB profile as registered information is maintained through F_1 to F_4 .

$$F_1 = \frac{R_{S1-S2} + R_{S1-S3} + R_{S1-S4}}{3} \quad (6)$$

$$F_2 = \frac{R_{S2-S1} + R_{S2-S3} + R_{S2-S4}}{3} \quad (7)$$

$$F_3 = \frac{R_{S3-S1} + R_{S3-S2} + R_{S3-S4}}{3} \quad (8)$$

$$F_4 = \frac{R_{S4-S1} + R_{S4-S3} + R_{S4-S3}}{3} \quad (9)$$

SBB PROFILE MATCHING

To match the SBB attributes, a variety of matching algorithms are available [33-35]. In this paper, a new kind of matching algorithm is introduced i.e., each SBB profile consists of four features, F1, F2, F3, and F4. Each one is computed based on SB attributes, such as re-tweets, replies, URLs, and hash-tags. Using the Euclidean distance formula mentioned in Eq. 10, the testing and registered SBB profiles are matched by computing distance between the corresponding features. Lastly, distance weights are considered as matching SBB profiles.

$$D_{F_i} = \sqrt{(F_{Ri} - F_{Ti})^2} \text{ Where } i = 1, 2, 3, 4 \quad (10)$$

Whereas D_{F_i} is the i th distance weight, F_{Ri} is the i th registered (R) feature, and F_{Ti} is the i th test (T) feature. Total four distance weights are computed. The distance weight is found by combining two features, test and registered, as bring up in Eq. 11-13.

$$D_{(F_1, F_i)} = \sqrt{((F_{R1} + F_{Ri}) - (F_{T1} + F_{Ti}))^2}, \quad i = 2, 3, 4 \quad (11)$$

$$D_{(F_2, F_i)} = \sqrt{((F_{R2} + F_{Ri}) - (F_{T2} + F_{Ti}))^2}, \quad i = 3, 4 \quad (12)$$

$$D_{(F_3, F_4)} = \sqrt{((F_{R3} + F_{R4}) - (F_{T3} + F_{T4}))^2} \quad (13)$$

Total three distance weights are computed from Eq. 11, two distance weights from Eq. 12, and one distance weight from Eq. 13. Finally, six distance weights calculated by combining two features at a time.

Find the distance weight by adding three features from the test and registered, them, as in Eq. 14.

$$D_{(F_1, F_2, F_3)} = \sqrt{((F_{R1} + F_{R2} + F_{R3}) - (F_{T1} + F_{T2} + F_{T3}))^2} \quad (14)$$

Similarly determine $D_{(F_2, F_3, F_4)}$, $D_{(F_3, F_4, F_1)}$, $D_{(F_4, F_1, F_2)}$ using Eq. 14. Adding four features F_1 , F_2 , F_3 , and F_4 of test and registered, then find the distance weight, as shown in Eq. 15.

$$D_{(F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4)} = \sqrt{((F_{R1} + F_{R2} + F_{R3} + F_{R4}) - (F_{T1} + F_{T2} + F_{T3} + F_{T4}))^2} \quad (15)$$

The above-mentioned distance weights are used for person identification.

PERSONAL IDENTIFICATION

THE FOLLOWING STEPS ARE USED FOR THE IDENTIFICATION OF A PERSON:

1. Find minimum distance weight

$$\min(D_{F_1}, D_{F_2}, D_{F_3}, D_{F_4})$$

$$\min(D_{(F_1, F_2)}, D_{(F_1, F_3)}, D_{(F_1, F_4)}, D_{(F_2, F_3)}, D_{(F_2, F_4)}, D_{(F_3, F_4)})$$

$$\min(D_{(F1,F2,F3)}, D_{(F2,F3,F4)}, D_{(F3,F4,F1)}, D_{(F4,F1,F2)})$$

Due to the fact that there is only one distance weight, it is not necessary to calculate the minimum distance weight based on a combination of four features.

2. There is a minimum distance weight assigned to each person, and then a threshold value is calculated using the average of those minimum distance weights.
3. Only weights greater than or equal to the threshold value are taken into account in the matching list.
4. Identification of a person whose weight is the minimum distance in the matching list.

The use of combined SBB feature profiles in biometrics improves the assurance of a person's authenticity by establishing more proofs of his authenticity. When two people have similar SBB profiles, they are less likely to have similar F_1 , F_2 , F_3 , and F_4 features and vice versa. The proposed work can get a more consistent outcome and also, SBB profiles can be used as security data during individual identification.

III. SYSTEM LEVEL ALGORITHM

1. The tweeter data of individual people should be collected month by month for a total of six months.
2. Focus on important text information in tweeter data by filtering out unnecessary marks and characters, and removing the tweets which occur repeatedly. Here's how it works: Provide the user's text. Take a look at the text character by character. In the case of alphabets and other mentioned special characters, do not add them to the text. When the character is an alphabet and mentions a special character, include it in the resultant text and save the text.
3. The tweet information is split along whitespace characters and returned as output-string cell arrays.
4. Each string cell array should be converted to a separate character cell array.
5. The monthly based URLs are collected by identifying the 'HTTP' characters in the character array, counting the total number of URLs, and storing them in a separate variable.
6. Similarly, collect the monthly hash-tags in a separate array using the '#' character and keep the weights of the hash-tags in a separate variable.
7. Identify the Re-Tweet characters in the character array for each node and count the total for each month, this is called the weight for that node. If the weight is less than five, the node is deleted.
8. Sum all the weights of each node for re-tweets.
9. Collect the replies to each node in a separate array by identifying the '@' characters in the character array for each month, then count the weights of that node, if the weight is less than five, that node is deleted.
10. To create reply nodes, step 7 and step 8 must be repeated.
11. Repeat steps 5 through 10 for six months for each person.
12. As illustrated in Table 1, arrange the table for a total sample of sessions per person in the

dataset.

13. In accordance with the equations mentioned in the section 2.2, calculate a person's PMCC for the six-month session.
14. As illustrated in Table 2, arrange the table as a sample of PMCC provided for a six-month period for a person.
15. Then extract the features for each person and keep a registered profile according to the equations described in the section 2.3.
16. Using Eq. 10 through Eq.15, calculate distance weights between the all registered SBBs and test SBB.
17. A person matching is authenticated in accordance with the procedure discussed in the section 2.5

IV RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Matlab2016b is utilized to accomplish the suggested performance of the system. The experiments were conducted on a Windows-7 operating system, 1.8 GHz quad-core Intel Core i5 processor and 4GB RAM. An online Twitter dataset of 100 users was compiled.

The dataset contains a total of six months of SB interactions between users and for every month tweeter information is recorded for the identical users. User interaction information includes four different attributes in tweets, shared URLs, re-tweets, replies, and shared hash-tags.

Table. 3 Performance comparison with features

Subjects	Registered -Test Distance weight				Minimum	Matching list	Identification
	D _{F1}	D _{F2}	D _{F3}	D _{F4}			
P ₁	0.2345	0.1267	0.0956	0.2145	0.0956	-	-
P ₂	0.2015	0.1545	0.1047	0.1835	0.1047	0.1047	A
P ₃	0.2151	0.1705	0.1285	0.1345	0.1285	0.1285	R
P ₄	0.2235	0.0785	0.2101	0.1402	0.0785	-	-

Table. 4 Two features matching

Subjects	Registered-Test Distance weight						Minimum	Matching list	Identification
	D (F1, F2)	D (F1, F3)	D (F1, F4)	D (F2, F3)	D (F2, F4)	D (F3, F4)			
P ₁	0.8339	0.7924	0.7717	0.7475	0.7268	0.6853	0.6853	0.6853	A
P ₂	0.9345	0.8123	0.7910	0.7894	0.7169	0.7848	0.7169	0.7169	R
P ₃	0.7345	0.7912	0.8121	0.7366	0.7389	0.8853	0.7345	0.7345	R
P ₄	0.8765	0.8213	0.7823	0.7871	0.8112	0.6876	0.6876	0.6876	R

Table. 5 Three features matching

Subjects	Registered-Test Distance weight				Minimum	Matching list	Identification
	D (F1, F2, F3)	D (F2, F3, F4)	D (F3, F4, F1)	D (F4, F1, F2)			
P ₁	1.1869	1.1267	1.9956	1.2145	1.1267	1.1267	R
P ₂	1.2015	1.1545	1.1047	1.1835	1.1047	1.1047	R
P ₃	1.2151	0.9705	1.1285	1.1345	0.9705	0.9705	A
P ₄	1.2235	0.9785	1.2101	1.1402	0.9785	0.9785	R

Table.3 demonstrates sample of how the matching of test distances and registered distances for person. Authentication is done by considering four different features. By compute the distance weight between the four features using Eq. 10 and then taking the minimum distance weight among them. The threshold value is computed according to section 2.5 for person authentication, practically speaking, it is 0.1. A minimum distance weight above the 0.1 is included in the matching process, and others are ignored. The minimum distance weight is taken into account for the authenticated person, and the rest will be rejected. P2 is the authenticated person in Table 3, set as A for Authentic, R for Reject.

Based on four different features and two features at a time, the authentication of the test with the registered person is shown in Table 4. Six distance weights are found by using Eq. 11-13. The minimum distance weight of the six are then tabulated. In the case of person authentication, the threshold is set at more than 0.5 practically. There are minimum distance weights above 0.5 that are included in the matching list, and among those weights, the minimum one is considered as authenticated one. P1 is the authenticated person in table 4.

Table 5 reveals that, matching the test and registered person authentication is done by considering four features with three being considered at a time, which are computed using Eq.14, i.e. four distance weights.

Tabulated the minimum distance weight among the four. Practically a threshold of 0.8 is set for person authentication. A minimum distance weight of above 0.8 is considered in the matching list, and among those distance weights minimum one is for the authenticated person. P3 is the authenticated person in Table 5.

Table 6. Four features matching

Subjects	Registered-Test Distance weight	Matching list	Identification
	D(F1,F2, F3, F4)		
P ₁	2.1867	2.1867	A
P ₂	2.2019	2.2019	R
P ₃	2.2153	2.2153	R
P ₄	1.4238	-	-

Table. 7 Average performance comparison by distance-weight

Registered -Test SBB Distance weight	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F-measure
$D_{\text{One-F}}$	84%	86%	83%	84%
$D_{\text{Two-F}}$	88%	90%	86%	87%
$D_{\text{Three-F}}$	90%	92%	88%	90%
$D_{\text{Four-F}}$	95%	96%	92%	93%

As described in Table 6, the four different features of the test and registered are considered during the person identification process. The distance weight D (F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4) is found by using Eq.15. A threshold of 1.5 is set for person authentication practically. Above 1.5 distances weight is considered in the matching list and among the list, a minimum distance weight for authenticated one.

The Table 7 shows the comparison of system performance with combination of features selection for calculating the distance weight i.e. $D_{\text{One-F}}$ represents the distance weights calculated using Eq. 10, $D_{\text{Two-F}}$ from Eq.11-13, $D_{\text{Three-F}}$ from Eq.14, $D_{\text{Four-F}}$ from Eq.15 respectively.

The average performance comparisons of system by distance-weights are affected by its features. When all four feature combinations are selected from registered and test SBB profile for calculating distance weight, it provides better authentication in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, F-measure, performance in the system.

The figure 4 shows the graphical representation of system performance comparison by distance-weight. If more feature combinations are included in the matching process, improves the system performances. SBB profile with different feature selection-based system measures in terms of F-measure, recall, precision, and accuracy after 5-fold cross-validation of identical registered and test datasets, as well as different test datasets. The results of the system performance comparison with different SBB profiles of persons with the same accuracy are shown in Table 7.

Furthermore, the system can also be examined to determine whether the person's SBB profile is likely to align with the way out with different SB feature selections, which are unique to supply enough involvement into the SBB systems.

Table 8 -11 show the assessment of the proposed system with different feature combinations, TA True Authentic, FA False Authentic, TR True Reject, and FR False Reject. Overall, the proposed system accuracy is higher for combination of four features than the others.

Fig 4: Graphical represent of the system performance with features

Table 8. Assessment of the proposed system with D_{Four-F}

Status	Authentic	Reject
True	TA=96 %	TR=94 %
False	FA=4 %	FR=6%
Over all system accuracy = 95%		
Specificity = 95 %		
Sensitivity =92 %		

Table 9. Assessment of the proposed system with $D_{Three-F}$

Status	Authentic	Reject
True	TA=92 %	TR=88 %
False	FA=8%	FR=12 %
Over all system accuracy = 90%		
Specificity = 92 %		
Sensitivity =88 %		
Status	Authentic	Reject
True	TA=90 %	TR=86%
False	FA=10 %	FR=14 %

Table 10. Assessment of the

proposed system with D_{Two-F}

Over all system accuracy = 88%

Specificity = 89 %

Sensitivity =86 %

Table 11. Assessment of the proposed system with D_{One-F}

Status	Authentic	Reject
True	TA=86%	TR=82 %
False	FA=14 %	FR=18 %

Over all system accuracy = 84%

Specificity = 85 %

Sensitivity =83 %

Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve is a graph that illustrates the ability to identify a person's authenticity or not. The test accuracy is determined by plotting the true authentication rate (sensitivity) against the false authentication rate (1-specificity). As the graph gets closer to the top and left-hand border, the accuracy increases. Furthermore, the system gives less accuracy when the graph is closer to the diagonal. Specificity is a measure of how well a dataset performs in the false authentication part, whereas sensitivity is a measure of how well it performs in the true authentication part.

Fig5: Illustration of the performance of the system based on ROCs

Table 12. Performance Comparison Table verify with papers

SBB Attributes	Accuracy
Re-tweet -networks [6]	89.00%
Hash-tag -networks [6]	52.00%
Replies-networks [6]	62.00%
URL-networks [6]	45.00%
Hash-tag-networks [5]	61.00%
URL-networks [5]	53.00%
Replies-networks [5]	68.00%
Re-tweet-networks [5]	90.00%
Bag-of-Words model with PMSVM [31]	68.74%
Proposed system	95%

In figure 5, the ROC curve with features is shown; the curve with four features (Four-F) is almost at the top and the left-hand border gives higher accuracy than the other Three-F, Two-F, and One-F curves. Based on four features' combination distance weight, the system gives overall good performance. The Table 12. shows the performance comparison of the proposed method with other SBB methods which are described in different research papers. The work presented in this paper has a greater accuracy than the other methods.

V. SUMMARY AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we analyze the individual person authentication performance by integrating features level system fusion to improve the overall accuracy of the SBB by analyzing the SBB profile. As per the previous survey on SBB, the proposed work is the first-time attempt to determine the impact of SB fusion based on the features within the SBB framework. According to the experimental test results, writing statements by users on OSN are more discriminatory in nature and have a very low error rate for person identification compared to the other SBB system. In addition, the feature level-based matching algorithm is better suited to SBB systems than other parameter-based fusion methods. It is a very simple approach with fewer system complexities and 95 % accuracy for person recognition. A feature-level fusion was recommended for a better trade-off between the accessible information and an easy integration into multimodal biometric systems. A better recognition rate will be achieved through the integration of SB profiles into biometric systems. The work contributes to an emerging trend in SBB research as remarkable. The proposed work can be used for person authentication using Twitter datasets. Additionally, the proposed work can be combined with other biometric modalities for better person identification based on SBB profiles.

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